

UNDERSTANDING OF THE INDEX SINCE DETERMINING THE LEVEL OF INVESTMENT RISKINESS

Turgunov Nodirjon Ma'rifjon o'g'li

Tashkent State University of Economics.

E-mail: nodirbekturgunov111@gmail.com

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Any investor begins to assess the investment environment of that country and territory, determine its attractiveness, before investing in a particular country and its territory. For a foreign investor, any factors affecting inertia are important. Therefore, in most developed countries, there are special firms, organizations that evaluate investment projects, study the investment climate of states that require investment, and provide clear conclusions and information for investors. For example: the prestigious information services of a number of countries, such as Switzerland, Germany, apply the "BERI" (business environment risk index), which takes into account 15 important indicators, each of which is assessed on a 4-point scale from "0" to "4" (0-unsatisfactory and 4-extremely favorable) to assess the economic, political and social status of the state.

The image below shows them based on their importance in making investment decisions.

The image shows that political stability (0.12 points) is the most important among the indicators included in the BERI index. According to the analysis, Western experts gave Georgia, Moldova, and Tajikistan the last places in the ratings precisely because of military actions or the escalation of the internal situation, as well as due to economic and political instability, that is, they "BERI" has the lowest index level. The essence of this method is that, based on the selection of reputable experts (generally, the total number of experts is about 100) and 15 main criteria on a 5-point scale (from 0 to 4 points and their sum is equal to 1) A country risk assessment is proposed. In this method, the evaluation criteria and their values are as follows:

- political stability (0.12);
- attitude to foreign investments (0.06);
- the risk of nationalization (0.06), if the law of the country provides for the expropriation of property without payment, 0 points are assigned;
- probability and level of currency devaluation (0.06);
- the state of the balance of payments (0.06);
- level of bureaucratization of business (0.04);
- economic growth rate (0.1);
- free exchange rate of the currency (0.1);
- the number of fulfillments of contractual obligations (0.06);
- level of labor productivity and wage costs (0.08);
- the possibility of obtaining legal and marketing advice, attracting qualified specialists (0.02);
- organization of communication and transport (0.04);
- relations of state bodies and public organizations (0.04);
- conditions for obtaining short-term loans (0.08);
- long-term loans, obtaining private capital, terms of use (0.08).

In general, "BERI" service is an organization that has gained a great reputation in this regard. This organization analyzes the investment environment in capital importing countries and determines the risk level of investments. "BERI" service determines the level of danger and risk of investors investing in foreign countries with various indices through the press. Currently, this service organization evaluates the investment climate in more than 55 capital importing countries with a criterion (score) covering 15 indicators. The higher the country's investment climate score, the more stable it is. The impact of political, economic, and social factors is also taken into account when calculating these

score indices. This organization evaluates not only the current period, but also the expected changes in the future.

References:

1. Vaxabov A.V., Xajibakiev Sh.X., Muminov N.G. Xorijiy investitsiyalar. O'quv qo'llanma. – T.: «Moliya», 2010. – B. 155-156.
2. Investitsiya va innovatsiya ma'ruza materiallari.
3. Ochilov, B., Hoshimov, J., & Butayev, J. (2024). IQTISODIYOTGA XORIJIY INVESTITSİYALARNI JALB ETISHDA MAMLAKAT INVESTITSION JOZIBADORLIGI: NAZARIYA VA AMALIYOT (Monografiya).
4. Navruzov, Ikram Abdullaevich. "THE ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF THE REGIONAL INVESTMENT ENVIRONMENT IN ATTRACTING FOREIGN INVESTMENTS TO THE ECONOMY." INNOVATSION IQTISODIYOTNI SHAKLLANTIRISHDA AXBOROT KOMMUNIKATSIYA TEXNOLOGIYALARINING TUTGAN O'RNI 1.1 (2023).
5. Tolaganova R., Ochilov B. DIRECTIONS FOR IMPROVING INVESTMENT ATTRACTION MECHANISMS //Евразийский журнал академических исследований. – 2024. – Т. 4. – №. 1 Part 2. – С. 144-151.
6. Vohidovich G. S. Leasing Procedure of Fixed Assets in Budget Organizations and their Expenditure //Indonesian Journal of Public Policy Review. – 2022. – Т. 18.
7. Murtazaevich, Khoshimov Sabir, and Ganiev Shahiriddin Vohidovich. "ISSUES OF INCREASING THE ATTRACTIVENESS OF THE INVESTMENT CLIMATE WHEN ATTRACTING INVESTMENTS INTO THE ECONOMY." (2024).
8. Suleymanov I. CONTEMPORARY ISSUES IN GLOBAL GEO-FINANCIAL POLICY AND THEIR IMPACT ON INTERNATIONAL FINANCIAL RELATIONS //Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 5. – С. 35-43.
9. Murtazaevich K. S. THE ROLE OF FOREIGN INVESTMENTS IN THE SOCIOECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF THE REGIONS //World Economics and Finance Bulletin. – 2023. – Т. 22. – С. 7-10.
10. Холмаматов, Ф. К. "Тижорат банкларининг кредитлаш амалиётини такомиллаштириш. И. ф. б. ф. д. дисс. автореф." И. ф. б. ф. д. илм. дар. ол. уч. тақд. эт. дисс. автореф.–Тошкент (2019).
11. Сулейманов И. БАНК ТИЗИМИ ВА ИҚТISОДИЁТНИНГ РЕАЛ СЕКТОРИ ИНТЕГРАЦИЯСИНИ ТАЪМИНЛАШ АСОСИДА ТИЖОРАТ БАНКЛАРИНИНГ РЕСУРС БАЗАСИНИ МУСТАҲКАМЛАШ МАСАЛАЛАРИ: https://doi.org/10.55439/ECED/vol23_iss5/a20 //Iqtisodiyot va ta'lim. – 2022. – Т. 23. – №. 5. – С. 122-129.

12. Хошимов Ж. Р., Очилов Б. Б., Наримонов С. С. ИНВЕСТИЦИОННАЯ ПОЛИТИКА: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА. – 2024.
13. Suleymanov I. R. STATE AND PROSPECTS OF INTERACTION OF THE BANKING SECTOR WITH THE REAL SECTOR OF THE ECONOMY OF UZBEKISTAN //International journal of Business, Management and Accounting. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 1.
14. Tursunkulovich S. R. et al. INCREASING THE LEVEL OF CAPITALIZATION AS A BASIS FOR STRENGTHENING FINANCIAL STABILITY IN COMMERCIAL BANKS //European Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development. – 2022. – Т. 4. – С. 201-207.
15. Kubayevich, K. F. . (2024). Current Analysis and Current Issues of Ensuring the Financial Stability of the Banking System in Uzbekistan. EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF BUSINESS STARTUPS AND OPEN SOCIETY, 4(3), 169–176.
16. Tursunkulovich S. R. ISSUES OF MONETARY REGULATION OF MONEY SUPPLY IN THE ECONOMY //American Journal of Business Management, Economics and Banking. – 2023. – Т. 12. – С. 1-11.
17. Sugahara, S., & Ochilov, B. (2023). The Experience of The Japanese State in Increasing Investment Activity in Uzbekistan.
18. Tursunkulovich S. R. SOME THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL EXPERIENSES REGULATION OF MONEY SUPPLY //Spectrum Journal of Innovation, Reforms and Development. – 2023. – Т. 16. – С. 60-71.